

MATE Awarded the HR Excellence in Research Recognition

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HR EXCELLENCE IN RESEARCH

The Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) has been awarded the **HR Excellence in Research Award** on **September 15, 2025**, becoming the **only Hungarian university** to receive this prestigious recognition to date. The award, granted by the European Commission, acknowledges institutions that demonstrate outstanding commitment to supporting researchers' careers, ensuring transparent and fair recruitment, and fostering a high-quality research environment.

Achieving this distinction was a **strategic goal of the ENT-R-E-NOVATORS Horizon Europe project**, carried out in **collaboration with the E3UDRES2 university alliance**, of which MATE is a key member. Furthermore, another Horizon Europe project, the AGRIGEP, supported this work, as Gender Equality is a key area of the Award. To obtain the award, MATE developed a comprehensive institutional strategy to ensure the implementation of the core principles **of the European Charter for Researchers and the Code of Conduct** for the Recruitment of Researchers.

Beyond enhancing international visibility and competitiveness, the HR Excellence in Research Award will help position MATE as an attractive employer for talented researchers from Hungary and abroad. This recognition proves that MATE operates according to the highest European standards and is dedicated to providing a supportive, innovative, and inspiring research environment, the University leadership emphasised.

The award represents a significant milestone in MATE's institutional development and transition process. It opens new opportunities for international research collaborations and strengthens the university's participation in **Horizon Europe** programs.

About MATE

The Hungarian University of Agriculture and Life Sciences (MATE) is a leading institution in Central Europe with a strong focus on agriculture, food sciences, environmental management, and sustainable development. With campuses across Hungary, MATE is committed to excellence in education, research, and innovation.

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